

Pattern of Maxillofacial Injuries due to Motorcycle Related Road Traffic Accidents at A Tertiary Care Hospital in Karachi, Pakistan

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ABSTRACT

Objective: To determine the frequency and pattern of maxillo-facial injuries related to motorcycle accidents and to find out the association of helmet use and maxillo-facial injuries

Methods: Two years (January 2014 - December 2015) retrospective data of maxillofacial trauma patients was collected from the department of Oral & Maxillofacial Surgery of Civil Hospital Karachi (CHK). Analysis, method?

Results: A total of 316 trauma patients were brought to the hospital during the study period. Out of these, 2.5% were children and 6.6% were adolescents. The majority 84.5% was aged 20 to 40 years, 5.4% were between 41 and 60 years and 1% were above 60 years of age. Males comprised 90.5% of the total. Total 8.9% had higher education while 15.2% were illiterate. Frequency of motorcyclists among the study patients was 84.2%. Out of these, 67.4% were drivers while 16.8% were passengers. Only 8.9% were wearing helmets. Soft tissue injuries were reported in 61.4% (194), 8.2% had dentoalveolar fractures, 47.78% mid-face fractures, 56% mandibular fractures, 61% isolated mandibular fractures and 39% presented with complex fractures. Twenty-nine percent had ZMC fractures, 92.6% were isolated ZMC, 9.5% had Le Fort II Fractures and 6% Le Fort III fractures; 5% had frontal sinus and 3.5% had pan-facial fractures. Significant relation was found between motorcyclists and helmet usage ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: Road Traffic Accidents are rising day by day in the developing countries. The causes include low use of safety devices, poor infrastructure, and rising number of vehicles on the roads. This study shows that mostly young men in their 20s and 30s are involved in these accidents. In more than 50% of these accidents, the mandible is fractured. The impact of this kind of injury on the young patients' quality of life is significant and traumatic. These fractures can be prevented by promoting the use of safety methods (mandatory wearing of crash helmets), improving road infrastructure, and regulating the number of registration of motorcycles. Safety regulations regarding helmet use need to be enforced strictly and awareness needs to be raised among the masses regarding safe use of motorcycles.

Key words: Road Traffic Accidents, Motorcycle Related Injuries, Maxillofacial Trauma

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عنوان: موٹرسائیکل حادثات کے نتیجے میں لگنے والی منہ اور جڑے کی چوٹوں کا جائزہ

مقصد: موٹرسائیکل کے حادثوں کے نتیجے میں لگنے والی منہ اور جڑے کی چوٹوں کی تعداد اور ان چوٹوں اور ہیلیمٹ کے استعمال کا تعلق معلوم کرنا۔

طریقہ: یہ عمومی جائزہ مول ہسپتال کراچی کے ڈیپارٹمنٹ برائے منہ کی سرجری میں کیا گیا جس میں دو سال (جنوری 2014- دسمبر 2015) میں آنے والے مریضوں کا ڈیٹا ریکارڈ سے حاصل کیا گیا۔

نتیجہ: اس مطالعے کے دوران 316 ٹریفک حادثے کے مریضوں کو ہسپتال لایا گیا۔ ان میں سے 84.2% فیصد موٹرسائیکل حادثوں میں جن میں سے 67.4% فیصد ڈرائیور تھے اور 16.8% فیصد مسافر صرف۔ 8.9% فیصد نے حادثے کے

وقت ہیلیمٹ پہنا ہوا تھا۔ اس مطالعے سے معلوم ہوتا ہے کہ زیادہ تر 20 سے 30 سال عمر کے جوان موٹرسائیکل حادثوں کا شکار ہوتے ہیں۔ اور پچاس فیصد سے زائد کم عمر میں نچلے جڑے پر چوٹ آتی ہے۔

حاصل مطالعہ: اس تحقیق سے معلوم ہوا کہ جوان مریضوں کی زندگی پر ایسی چوٹوں کا گہرا اثر ہوتا ہے۔ ہیلیمٹ کے استعمال سے ایسی چوٹوں سے بچا جاسکتا ہے۔ ہیلیمٹ کے استعمال سے متعلق قوانین کو سختی سے لاگو کرنے کی

ضرورت ہے اور عوام میں اس سے متعلق شعور پیدا کرنا ضروری ہے۔

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INTRODUCTION

Human face is anatomically divided into three segments that is tripartite composition^{1,2}. These segments, from inside to outside, are (1) hard tissue, (2) soft tissue (muscles fats and subcutaneous connective tissue, and (3) skin superficial layer².

Presently in western countries, assault is becoming the most frequent cause of facial trauma³ but in the developing world, road traffic accidents are among the

most common causes of maxillofacial fractures³⁻⁵. A huge difference has been observed between developed and developing countries that may be because of stringent implementation of laws and regulations in developed countries. As many as 39%⁴ to 54%³ of all maxillofacial traumas in Pakistan are related to road traffic accidents⁶.

Two-wheel vehicle (motorcycle) is considered as the riskiest vehicle ever due to its design, balancing issues, and absences of installed safety devices like airbags. Absence of a safety vessel around the driver and the passenger make both vulnerable to crashes during collision or slipping⁷. Many other risk factors compound the situation including the condition and nature of the roads, traffic flow, poor visibility at night as well as the human factors: the attitude and behaviour of motorcyclists on the roads, speeding, ignoring safety measures like wearing crash helmets and protective clothing, alcohol and substance abuse prior to riding⁸.

In Pakistan, comprehensive information about the epidemiological characteristic of this problem is needed in view of the great impact of maxillofacial traumatic injuries on a person's quality of life. This study would help to identify the anatomical site of fractures and associated injuries, to evaluate the frequency of maxillofacial trauma, the incidence of fractures while riding a motorcycle, and the pattern of maxillofacial injuries sustained by helmet-wearing or non-helmet-wearing motorcyclists.

METHODOLOGY

Retrospective data of maxillofacial trauma patients, irrespective of age and gender was included and patients having pathological fractures from other causes were excluded from the study. Patients admitted at the department of oral and maxillofacial surgery of Civil Hospital Karachi (CHK), a tertiary care teaching hospital, were included in study. The duration of the study was two years (from January 2014 to December 2015). All data collected was consequently processed and analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version-17 for statistical analysis and descriptive variables.

RESULTS

Total 316 trauma patients registered with maxillofacial department of Civil Hospital, Karachi during the study period. Eight of the patients (2.5%) were children and 21 (6.6%) were adolescents. Most of the patients 84.5% (267) were between the ages of 20 to 40 years. Total 5.4% patients (17) were middle aged 41-60 years and 1% (3) were older than 60 years of age. Over all, 90.5%

(n=286) patients were male. Twenty-eight patients (8.9%) had education higher than intermediate while 15.2% were illiterate. Frequency of motorcyclists among study patients was 84.2% (n=266), out of whom 80% (n=213) were drivers while 20% (n=53) were passengers. All those riding as passengers on the motorcycles, were not wearing helmets while only 11% (n=28) of drivers were wearing helmets. Percentage of road traffic accidents during the day was 58% and 42% in the night.

There were 61.4% (n=194) patients with soft tissue injuries out of whom only 2.6% (n=5) patients had only soft tissue injuries without facial fractures and were admitted to the department. Twenty-six patients (8.2%) had dentoalveolar fractures. A total of 151 fracture were reported in the midface region (48%). Mandible, the lower jaw bone, was fractured in 177 patients (56%). Out of these, 62% (n=109) were isolated mandibular fractures and 39% (n=69) were complex fractures. Total 29% (n=91) had ZMC, out of whom 92.6% (n=75) had isolated ZMC fractures and others were concomitant with other fractures. As many as 9.5% (n=30) had Le Fort II Fractures and 6% (n=19) had Le Fort III fractures. Five percent (n=16) had frontal sinus fractures and 3.5% (n=11) patients had sustained pan-facial fractures.

Sixteen patients (5%) were managed conservatively, 45 patients (14%) were managed with closed reduction ± MMF while 250 (79%) patients were managed with open reduction and internal fixation. Five patients (2%) had to go through both ORIF with MMF. Significant relation of safety helmets was checked with mandibular fractures (complex and compound). Midface fractures (Le Fort I, II, III, and ZMC fractures), pan-facial and frontal bone fractures?????. No significant relation of the use of safety helmet was found with the above-mentioned variables except with ZMC fractures which was found to be significant (p= 0.05). Le Fort I and Le Fort II fractures were more common in bikers as compared to three-wheel and four-wheel vehicle users (p= 0.05).

DISCUSSION

Maxillofacial region involves soft and hard tissues forming the face extending from frontal bone superiorly to the mandible inferiorly⁹. The face, being the most exposed part of the body, is particularly prone to trauma¹⁰. Facial traumatic insults include soft and hard tissues including teeth, alveolus, jaw bones, and specialized structures such as eyes, ears, and nose.

Table No. 1: Detailed Distribution of Maxillofacial Injury Patients

		Gender		Qualifications		Victim status			Vehicle Status		Safety device	
		Male	Female	=Inter	=Graduate	Driver	Passenger	Pedestrian	Bikers	Others	Helmet/ seat belts	NO safety device
Gender	Male	286 (90.5%)	30 (9.5%)	262 (82.9%)	24 (7.6%)	237 (75%)	36 (11.4%)	13 (4.1%)	246 (77.8%)	40 (12.7%)	2 (0.6%)	28 (8.9%)
	Female			26 (8.2%)	4 (1.3%)	0 (0%)	24 (7.6%)	6 (1.9%)	20 (6.3%)	10 (3.2%)	28 (8.9%)	2 (0.6%)
Qualifications	=Inter	262 (82.9%)	26 (8.2%)	288 (91.1%)	28 (8.9%)	216 (68.4%)	55 (17.4%)	17 (5.4%)	246 (77.8%)	42 (13.3%)	30 (9.5%)	258 (81.6%)
	> Inter	24 (7.6%)	4 (1.3%)			21 (6.6%)	5 (1.6%)	2 (0.6%)	20 (6.3%)	8 (2.5%)	2 (0.6%)	26 (8.2%)
Victim status	Driver	237 (75.0%)	0 (0.0%)	216 (68.4%)	21 (6.6%)	237 (75%)	60 (19%)	19 (6%)	213 (67.4%)	24 (7.6%)	29 (9.2%)	208 (65.8%)
	Passenger	36 (11.4%)	24 (7.6%)	55 (17.4%)	5 (1.6%)				53 (16.8%)	7 (2.2%)	3 (0.9%)	57 (18.0%)
	Pedestrian	13 (4.1%)	6 (1.9%)	17 (5.4%)	2 (.6%)				0 (0.0%)	19 (6.0%)	0 (0%)	19 (6.0%)
Vehicle Status	Bikers	246 (77.8%)	20 (6.3%)	246 (77.8%)	20 (6.3%)	213 (67.4%)	53 (16.8%)	0 (0.0%)	266 (84.2%)	50 (15.8%)	32 (10.1%)	234 (74.1%)
	Others	40 (12.7%)	10 (3.2%)	42 (13.3%)	8 (2.5%)	24 (7.6%)	7 (2.2%)	19 (6.0%)		0 (0%)	50 (15.8%)	
Safety device	Helmet/ seat belts	30 (9.5%)	2 (0.6%)	30 (9.5%)	2 (0.6%)	25 (7.9%)	5 (1.6%)	2 (0.6%)	28 (8.9%)	4 (1.3%)	32 (10.1%)	284 (89.9%)
	NO safety device	256 (81.0%)	28 (8.9%)	258 (81.6%)	26 (8.2%)	212 (67.1%)	55 (17.4%)	17 (5.4%)	238 (75.3%)	46 (14.6%)		

Table No. 2: Distribution of Mandibular Fracture with Respect to Complexity of Fracture

		Isolated / Complex Mandibular Fracture		
		No Fracture	Isolated Mandibular Fracture	Complex Mandibular Fracture
Mandible	No Fractures	140 44.3%		
	Fracture	0 0%	111 35.1%	65 20.6%
Dentoalveolar Region	No Injury	130 41.1%	102 32.3%	58 18.4%
	Dentoalveolar Injury	10 3.2%	9 2.8%	7 2.2%
Angle of Mandible	No Fractures	140 44.3%	91 28.8%	17 5.4%
	Angle Fracture	0 0%	20 6.3%	48 15.2%
Parasymphysis Region	No Fractures	140 44.3%	60 19.0%	17 5.4%
	Parasymphysis Fracture	0 0%	51 16.1%	48 15.2%
Mandibular Condylar	No Fractures	140 44.3%	71 22.5%	37 11.7%
	Condyle Fracture		40 12.7%	28 8.9%

Table No. 3: Distribution of Maxillary Fracture with Respect to Complexity of Fracture

		Isolated / Complex Midface Fracture		
		No Fracture	Isolated Midface Fracture	Complex Midface Fracture
Midface Fractures	No Fractures	165 52.2%		
	Fracture	0 0%	135 42.7%	16 5.1%
Le Fort I	No Fractures	165 52.2%	123 38.9%	14 4.4%
	Le Fort I Fracture	0 0%	12 3.8%	2 .6%
Le Fort II	No Fracture	165 52.2%	107 33.9%	14 4.4%
	Le Fort II Fracture		28 8.9%	2 0.6%
Le Fort III	No Fractures	165 52.2%	120 38.0%	12 3.8%
	Le Fort III Fracture		15 4.7%	4 1.3%
ZMC Fracture	No Fractures	165 52.2%	55 17.4%	5 1.6%
	ZMC Fracture		80 25.3%	11 3.5%

Figure 1: Frequency of Helmet Usage Among Motorcyclist

Figure 2: Distribution of Treatment Provided to Maxillofacial Injury Patients

ncidence of maxillofacial trauma is significantly increasing in Pakistan both in severity as well as frequency⁴. The causes of maxillofacial trauma vary and include RTAs, interpersonal violence, falls, sports and missile injuries¹¹⁻¹³. Maxillofacial injuries are the most commonly attributed to Road Traffic Accidents^{14,15}. Third world countries have issues in implementation of traffic regulations strictly in addition to low-level infrastructure and deficiencies in urban transport network. This leads to the increased incidence of motorized vehicle injuries as motorcycle is considered a convenient and cheap transport vehicle for goods and pillion passengers¹⁶. Face is a prominent part of body which is exposed while riding a motorcycle, if not protected with helmet. Absence of helmet makes both driver and passenger vulnerable to maxillofacial injuries^{17,18}.

Asian Countries have higher dependency on motorcycles because they are inexpensive, readily available, and easy to maintain leading to rising numbers of their registration¹⁹ (Motorcycles registrations comprise 95%²⁰, 67%²¹, and 63%²¹, of all registered vehicles in Vietnam, Taiwan, and Malaysia, respectively). By contrast, , motorcycling is undertaken as a form of recreation and leisure in the developed countries, for example in the United States of America, motorcycles comprise 2% of registered motor vehicles²².

In western industrialized countries, 65 to 67% of maxillofacial trauma is caused by Road Traffic Injuries (RTAs)^{23,24}. Chinese population shows a low incidence of 31%²⁵. While in Pakistan, RTAs contribute to about 56% of maxillofacial trauma⁶. Obekue et al²⁶ reported motorcycle crashes as the second commonest cause (27.2%) of maxillofacial injuries in 312 patients studied in Nigeria. Ogini et al⁷ reported that injuries to soft tissue were the most prevalent, followed bony and dental injuries (38%,15%) respectively in 221 studied patients also in Nigeria.

Motorcycle is considered to be a dangerous motorized vehicle due to its nature and design e.g. absence of airbags to reduce impact in the event of a collision and therefore riders and passengers alike are vulnerable to road traffic crashes⁷. Risk factors include the condition and nature of the roads, traffic flow, poor visibility at night while human factors include the attitude and behaviour of motorcyclists on the roads, speeding, ignoring safety measures like wearing of crash helmets and protective clothing, alcohol and substance abuse prior to riding⁸.

RTAs are a global health problem and the leading cause of maxillofacial trauma worldwide²⁶. The pattern and presentation of maxillofacial injuries have been studied in many parts of the world with varying results. Rodrigues et al. carried out a cross-sectional study in Brazil and reported the RTA in 45.7% traumas resulted with motorcycle crashes and 18.9% were mainly responsible for RTA²⁷.

In Nigeria, various studies, which are mainly hospital based, have documented the road traffic accidents as the main reasons for maxillofacial injuries all over the country except for in the North zone where assault is the main cause²⁶.

South Asia is a region where maxillofacial trauma resulting from RTA has been rising steadily over the past decades and is expected to increase by two and half times in the next two decades¹⁹.

The demographic pattern in this study is similar to previous studies by Oginni et al⁷, Oginni et al²⁸; Iribhogbe, P.E & Odai²⁹. The peak incidence of maxillofacial injuries is in the second and third decades of life i.e. victim is aged between 21 and 40 years.

The most prominent mechanisms responsible for crashes were found to be head on collisions, slips, and speeding. The reasons could be low maintenance of roads, inexperienced driving, and disobeying traffic rules. Another important finding was the low prevalence of helmet use at only 8.9% which is again almost similar to Oginni et al⁷. The relevant authorities should enforce the use of helmets to reduce maxillofacial injuries.

CONCLUSION

Road traffic Accidents are rising in the developing countries and becoming a leading cause of Maxillofacial Injuries. The present study provides a relevant pattern and outcome of victims involved in these injuries with the highest occurrence reported in the younger population. The main contributory factor is accidents involving motorcyclists with low use of safety devices.

Road Traffic Accidents are predictable and preventable provided the basic knowledge and awareness regarding safety measures and traffic rules is given to people. More research is needed to implement the measures that have reduced RTAs in developed countries like regulating the public transportation systems, enforcing safety registrations, and restrictions on mobile-phone use while driving. It is imperative that the government should make this issue a priority. Registration of motorcycles should be reduced to match the infrastructure and traffic load of cities.

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